

Experimental study on a fin-plate connection under a column-loss event

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the performance of fin-plate connections exposed to a column-loss scenario. For the experimental investigation, quasi-static and dynamic tests were carried out on an assembly of short steel sections. The dimensions of the cross-sections were chosen such, that bearing resistance in the beam web provided the least resistance, resulting in a ductile failure mode. The experimental study showed consistent deformations at low and high loading rates, with shear-out failure being the main failure mode. Additionally, a numerical model in Abaqus was used to analyse the load transfer in the connection. It was found that the arching forces due to contact between the beam flange and the column flange significantly increased the resistance of the connection. However, the tested fin-plate connection exhibited low energy absorption and would therefore perform poorly in the event of a column-loss.

Keywords: Fin-plate, bearing capacity, shear-out failure, column-loss

1 INTRODUCTION

Conventional steel structures are currently designed according to design standards. In Europe the Eurocode EN 1993 (1) is used while in America the AISC (2) offers standards for the design and construction of steel structures. Focusing on the Eurocode, the design rules are limited to static loading except for fatigue analysis and seismic loading. Low probability events such as blast loading or impact loading are currently not covered by the standards. Guidelines for design for impact loading is given in 1991-1-7 (3) which states that dynamic loads should be replaced by equivalent static loads resulting in the same deformations to evaluate the structural integrity. Derived as the equivalent static load for a single degree of freedom (SDOF) system, an amplification factor of 2 is suggested and as shown by Izzudin (4), SDOF systems can be assumed as an upper limit for column loss scenarios. However, the dynamic amplification factor of 2 implies that only elastic deformations occur in the structure, leading to overly conservative design as shown by Izzudin (4), if the structural components deform plastically. Therefore, also the EC 1991-1-7 (3) suggests that the plastic strength of the members should be considered in an impact scenario, especially if the structure is designed to dissipate energy during the impact. Yet, there are no guidelines present in the EC covering the design of joint connection in an impact scenario.

In a column loss scenario redistribution of the load to the surrounding structural members is required. The joint connection, which is the weakest link in a structure, will then be exposed to a significant increase in load. The possible redistribution of the load to supporting structural components depends on sufficient ductility and rotation capacity of the joint. While there is only few experiments carried out dynamically to investigate the performance of steel joint connections during a sudden column loss scenario (5-8) most experiments are based on quasi-static experiments removing the support at the place of the lost column (9-11). However, by this approach possibly strain rate effects and inertia effects may be neglected.

Therefore, the contribution of this study is to investigate the resistance of fin-plate connections at both low and high loading rates.

Fin-plate connections are commonly used in Norway, due to their fast and easy erection. As they are designed to transfer vertical loads, they are in general a popular choice for non-seismic areas.

2 TEST SPECIMEN

For the experimental test campaign, a configuration of short steel sections was used, as shown in Figure 1. The beams and the column of the connection are made of IPE160 and HEB220 sections respectively, each with a steel grade of S355. The fin-plate was welded to the column with a continuous fillet weld and the beams were fastened with two M20 bolts of steel grade 10.9. The dimensions of the components were chosen to facilitate bearing failure in the beam web as the governing failure mode, given that ductile failure modes are favourable in impact scenarios. The pitch and end distances of the bolts were set to comply with the minimum required distances given by the Eurocode. As common in practice the fin-plate was installed on one side of the beam and centred with the column web. To avoid contact forces between the beam flanges and the fin-plate during the rotation of the beams the top corner of the fin-plate was bevelled.

The mechanical properties of the IPE and HEB profile were identified by means of uniaxial tensile testing on cylindrical test coupons, yielding an ultimate tensile stress of 580 MPa and 540 MPa, respectively. The fin-plate was made of a cut-out from the HEB220 web. As the bolts were dimensioned to deform only elastically, nominal values for the elastic material behaviour were adopted.

Figure 1: Test specimen (a) and detailed view of the joint region (b), dimensions given in mm.

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

The test program comprised the performance of two repeated tests under both quasi-static and high load conditions. For both loading cases, the beams were fork supported at a distance of 700 mm from the column, to prevent lateral and out-of-plane movement. However axial restraint of the beams was intentionally excluded to ensure same boundary conditions for both loading rates and for replicable testing.

As depicted in Figure 2, a hydraulic actuator was affixed to the column using a bolted grip in the quasi-static test, exerting an upward pulling force on the joint connection at a consistent loading rate of 0.2 mm/sec. Measurements of force and displacement were recorded through a load cell positioned between the hydraulic actuator and the bolted grip.

Figure 2: Schematic presentation of quasi-static test set-up

In the dynamic test, a trolley with mass 440 kg and velocity 10m/s hit the specimen, as illustrated in Figure 3. The test specimen was mounted in an upright position in the dynamic test. Some modifications to the joint connection were made in comparison to the quasi-static test. The column was shortened at the end adjacent to the rigid wall, enabling sufficient deformation. Additionally, a thick steel plate was welded to the front end of the column to redistribute the load from the impact.

Figure 3: Schematic presentation of the pendulum accelerator (13), used for the dynamic tests.

The impact force of the trolley was recorded by a load cell positioned at the front of the trolley at a frequency of 250000 Hz. Two high-speed cameras were set up to record the deformations of the joint connection at 25000 Hz. Using digital image correlation (DIC) techniques, the displacement of the column could be determined. Additional information about the instrumentation can be found in Obkircher et al. (12).

4 CONCLUSION

Based on the insights gained from this study analysing the performance of fin-plate connections under a column-loss scenario following conclusions can be drawn:

- In a column-loss scenario where the axial restraint of the beams can be limited or non-existent, the shear force resistance in the joint connection is significantly reduced. This is due to the fact that a moment is generated in the connection to transfer the loads and as a consequence the bolts are mostly loaded perpendicular to the load direction.
- The resistance of fin-plate connections increases considerably at large beam rotations, as the gap between the beam and the column closes. The maximum resistance is however limited by the bearing resistance of the components.
- Consistent deformations and failure modes were observed across the loading rates. Despite dynamic loading of the fin-plate connection resulting in higher energy absorption, fin-plate connections exhibit overall low energy absorption, making them unsuitable in column-loss scenarios.

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